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Specific Features Of Adaptive Didactic Training Of Future Oligophrenopedagogues

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Annotation: The thesis analyzes the specific features of forming the adaptive didactic training of future oligophrenopedagogues from scientific-theoretical and practical perspectives. Special attention is paid to adapting the educational process when working with children with intellectual disabilities, taking into account their individual abilities and needs, as well as the adaptive application of teaching methods and pedagogical technologies.

Key words: Adaptive didactics, training of oligofrenopedagogues, sensory methods, grammatization, professional competencies.

Introduction.

Today, one of the relevant directions of the theory and practice of higher pedagogical education is the process of forming professionally important qualities of future specialists. Different views on the professional activity of a teacher have led to different approaches to the definition of necessary personal and professional qualities and their content. In the first case, professionally important qualities are understood as a set of knowledge, skills and qualifications that a teacher must possess in order to effectively perform his professional duties. In the second, this is a set of personal qualities that ensure a positive result of pedagogical activity. In such difficult conditions, special attention should be paid by society and the state to the problem of high-quality selection and professional and personal training of future oligophrenopedagogues. K.D. The following words of Ushinsky very clearly reflect the essence of the problem: "We do not tell educators to do this, but not otherwise; we do not tell them: study the laws of the psychic phenomena that you want to control and act in accordance with these laws and the situations that you want to apply. Not only are these conditions extremely diverse, but the nature of the students is also not similar to each other. Is it possible to establish any recipes for education when the conditions of education and the individuals being educated are so diverse? That is why we advise educators to study the physical and spiritual nature of a person as thoroughly as possible, to study their students and the situation surrounding them, to study history. N.V. Alishev, A.S. Yegorov, N.B. Rebrova in their research "Development of professionally important functions as one of the directions of improving the preparation of students" (published in the scientific collection "certain

professionally important characteristics or parameters by which the effectiveness and reliability of human activity are assessed" are understood. According to V.L. Marishuk, professionally important qualities are individual dynamic characteristics of a person, certain mental and psychomotor characteristics, physical qualities that correspond to the requirements of the profession imposed on a person and help to successfully master this profession. In the study of Ye.V. Shivrin, the professional norms, standards of behavior and activity of a special education teacher were identified and described, and their formation occurred under the influence of many deontological concepts. The author distinguishes informal and formal norms of behavior of a teacher-defectologist. Informal norms are defined as systems of "oral law" that are passed down from generation to generation and constitute the main moral and pedagogical concepts of pedagogical activity. It follows that the result of the formation of professionally important qualities is the ability of the future teacher-defectologist to meet the requirements of the profession. There must be a set of specific professional knowledge, skills, and personal qualities that respond to the task.

In turn, the set of specified qualities of a person should consist of a unity of moral, psychological and professional components (ideological-political, professional awareness, personal experience in the chosen profession, personal position in choosing a profession, duty and responsibility, teamwork, camaraderie, diligence, organization in work). O. V. Druzhilovskaya noted that the higher pedagogical school educates a specialist who, using special teaching methods, helps to form the child's personality and forms an adaptive mechanism of interaction with others. According to the author, the goal of defectological education is to train a specialist with a high level of professional competence, which determines a positive psychological orientation to work with various categories of children with developmental and health problems. Professional education is a combination of the professional and personal sphere of the oligophrenopedagogue and the level of formation of his professional knowledge, skills and qualifications. The specific features of the adaptive didactic training of future oligophrenopedagogues require the formation of a number of specific professionally significant qualities at the stage of professional training in the conditions of a higher pedagogical educational institution. The goal of defectological education is not only to train a specialist with a high level of professional competence, but also to form a positive psychological orientation for future activities in the upbringing and education of various categories of children with special educational needs. Adaptive didactic training of future oligophrenopedagogues ensures the effectiveness of working with children with intellectual disabilities. Adaptation of the educational process, consideration of

individual needs and adaptive use of teaching methods are important factors in the development of professional competencies of future specialists.

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